

**17th Central European Lung Cancer Conference
including
Best of WCLC 2018**

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Dear colleagues,

It is our pleasure to welcome you to the 17th Central European Lung Cancer Conference including Best of WCLC 2018. The Conference is organized by Institute for Pulmonary Diseases in Sremska Kamenica and Central European Lung Cancer Association – CELCA.

The aim of CELCC is to develop strategies for decreasing the burden of lung cancer in Europe. Therefore, we invite different specialists working in the field of lung cancer to participate at the CELCC 2018.

Thank you for your highly appreciated contribution to this Conference.

We wish you a pleasant and rewarding stay in Novi Sad!

On behalf of the Organizing Committee, sincerely,

Prof. Dr Ilija Andrijević
Conference President

Prof. Dr Nevena Secen
Conference President

Prof. Dr Robert Pirker
Member of the Board CELCA

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LONG-TERM SURVIVOR SCLC – CASE REPORT

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INTRODUCTION: Small cell lung carcinoma is a very aggressive form of cancer, accounts for 10-15% of all lung cancers. Diagnosis at an early stage improve the prognosis of the disease.

CASE REPORT: We are presenting case of 71 years old female, smoker, diagnosed with stage III A (T2bN2M0) small cell lung carcinoma, with a good performance status. The patient had a chronic obstructive pulmonary disease as an associated disease. Initial CT scan of thorax showed infiltrative lesion of 57mm in right lung hilum with atelectasis of upper and middle lobes and mediastinal lymphadenopathy 4R- 21mm. CT scan of head pointed to old ischemic lesions. Chemotherapy fourth cycle with Etoposid+Cisplatina combined with competitive chest radiotherapy in dose 40Gy/20fr was performed. Conformal chest radiotherapy started after second cycle of chemotherapy. When combined treatment chemotherapy with radiotherapy finished, in the continuation of treatment prophylactic whole brain radiotherapy in dose 20Gy was performed. During treatment patient's performance status was good and without significant side effects.

After above mentioned therapy procedures the patient was radiologic followed for 6-year (CT scan, PET CT, chest X ray, abdominal US) which showed SD. The last CT scan of thorax in May 2017 pointed to the postradiation state with the sequences, both sides more extensively to the right, with no signs of the cancer dissemination of the underlying disease, with infiltrative nodus in the right lung. Patient was alive 7 years after diagnosis, with no evidence of relaps. In October 2017 the patient died due the worsening of a chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.

CONCLUSION: Early diagnosis and multimodal therapy of patients with SCLC is important for long-term survival.

KEYWORDS: Small cell lung cancer, chemotherapy, radiotherapy, long-term survival

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